

Integrated pest management—insects

Hibernation sites of the rice stalk stink bug *Tibraca limbativentris* in the central region of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil

D. Link, J. G. Naibo, and J. P. Pelentir,
Departamento de Defesa Fitossanitaria,
Centro de Ciencias Rurais-UFSM, 97119-
900, Santa Maria-RS, Brazil

We surveyed the preferential sites where the rice stalk stink bug (RSSB) *Tibraca limbativentris* (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae), an important irrigated rice pest in southern Brazil, hibernates between growing seasons. Visual observation of densely massed plants was made. The insects were counted in each plant located 2.5-100 m away from field borders.

In 1992, we surveyed fallow fields in three counties: five in Sao Sepe, two in

Average number of bugs on some plant species. Santa Maria, Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil, 1992-94.

Species	Bushes (no.)	Bugs bush ⁻¹ (no.)	Standard deviation	Range
1992-93				
<i>Eryngium eburneum</i> ^a	330	33.99	0.86	5-100
<i>Erianthus</i> sp. ^b	330	14.00	1.57	1-101
<i>Andropogon lateralis</i> ^b	330	9.17	0.69	1-24
<i>Paspalum urvillei</i> ^b	330	5.73	0.93	1-26
<i>Baccharis trimeris</i> ^c	330	2.20	1.20	1-10
<i>Panicum prionites</i> ^b	330	2.14	0.70	1-3
<i>Senecio brasiliensis</i> ^c	330	1.10	1.15	1-5
1993-94				
<i>Andropogon lateralis</i> ^b	600	11.58	1.22	1-100
<i>Schizachyrium microstachyum</i> ^b	600	6.89	0.71	1-30
<i>Eryngium eburneum</i> ^a	600	5.02	1.01	1-29
<i>Paspalum urvillei</i>	600	2.86	0.69	3-23

^aApiaceae (=Umbelliferae), ^bPoaceae (=Gramineae),
^cAsteraceae (=Compositae).

Agudo, and three in Santa Maria. In 1993, 20 fallow fields in Santa Maria were visited. Fields that were flooded after harvest or were not infested during the growing season were not included.

Higher RSSB populations were observed on the bigger and more compact clusters, which provide an ideal refuge for both adult and young forms.

The bugs were near the soil surface where air moisture is higher. More than 90% of the hibernating forms were located up to 10 m from the field border. The distribution of the hibernating forms of RSSB was observed at 2.5, 5.0, 7.5, 10, 15, 25, 50, and 100 m from the field border. For each site, 10 samples were collected from a 2-m² area. More than 40 plant species were found to shelter RSSB, but the last four species listed were preferred by the bugs (see table). ■

Integrated pest management—weeds

Predicting the effects of *Echinochloa crus-galli* on rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) using the ecophysiological model INTERCOM

F. J. Abamu, IRRRI

Weed research is now focused on finding alternative methods to control weeds as well as on understanding new concepts that underlie weed management. To support this new approach, tools that can be used to understand the complexities of crop-weed relations and to predict weed effects are important.

Between 1994 and 1995, we conducted field experiments and simulation studies at IRRRI to evaluate the ability of an ecophysiological crop-weed competition model (INTERCOM) to simulate the effects on rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) of competition from different densities of a weed (*Echinochloa crus-galli* L. Beauv), emerging at different times, and allowed to grow with the crop for the rest of the season. A split-plot exper-

imental design was used. Weed density and time of weed emergence/flush were the treatments.

There were three weed density levels — 0, 20, and 40 plants m⁻² (designated as weed-free check, low, and high densities, respectively). All weed populations were introduced artificially. To imitate natural conditions in which weeds emerge in different flushes, the weed density treatments were controlled in such a way that weeds emerge at two separate times in the ricefield. These were 2-5 d after rice transplanting (DAT) (early emergence) and 12-15 DAT (late emergence). Nitrogen was applied at a rate of 150 kg ha⁻¹.

Simulation runs were made with weather data of 6 yr, including the actual year of experimentation.

Results showed that time of weed emergence was a more critical factor than weed density. Competition from weeds that emerged late (both high and low densities) did not have significant (P>0.05) effects on rice. This is because the cultivar used (IR72)

closed its canopy at about 25-30 DAT, thereby increasing the shade over the late-emerging weeds and limiting the light capture ability of this set of weeds for the benefit of the rice crop. It has been reported that the growth, development, and competitiveness of the weeds (*Echinochloa*) are adversely affected by shade.

When the seeds emerged early, rice plant height did not significantly (P>0.05) respond to competition from both high and low weed densities, whereas there were significant (P<0.05) reductions in rice leaf area index (LAI) from maximum tillering. The model comparison for plant height prediction showed that INTERCOM adequately simulated rice height from transplanting to maturity. Simulated and observed heights at maturity did not differ significantly (P>0.05). The pattern of simulated LAI development in time was also similar to that observed, but deviation of the observed from the simulated was significant (P>0.05) around maximum LAI. LAI was underpredicted at this growth stage in most

1. Response of observed and simulated grain yield of rice to competition from different densities of weeds (*Echinochloa crus-galli*) emerging at different times. IRRI, 1994-95.

2. Comparison between simulated and observed dry matter of rice from transplanting to maturity. In the legend, ds and ws = crop seasons (dry and wet), H and L = weed densities (high [40], and low [20] plants m⁻²) 1 and 2 = time of weed emergence (1 = early [2-5 DAT], 2 = late [12-15 DAT]). IRRI, 1994-95.

treatments, suggesting a need to further evaluate the model's ability to predict LAI.

Dry matter production and grain yield (Fig. 1) were significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced by competition from early-emerging weeds. Reduction was greater at high than at low weed density. Simulated and observed grain yields across all weed densities and time of weed emergence treatment combinations were highly correlated ($R = 0.97^{**}$) and did not differ significantly ($P > 0.05$). Simulated and observed dry matter content from transplanting to maturity were also correlated ($R = 0.92^{**}$) (Fig. 2).

INTERCOM can provide insights into the effects of *Echinochloa* competition on rice when the crop receives adequate N, irrespective of time of weed flush or weed density. ■

Weed control in direct seeded puddled rice

P. S. Bisht, P. C. Pandey, and P. Lal, Agronomy Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Nainital 263145, India

Weed control in direct seeded rice is a serious problem in northern India. Manual weeding controls weeds effectively but availability and cost of labor limit its adoption. There are safe and nonphytotoxic herbicides, but their effectiveness has not yet been evaluated.

Butachlor, pendimethalin, and thio-bencarb are the recommended herbicides, but at least one additional hand weeding is required with these. The use of safener, an antiphytotoxicity compound that eliminates the toxic effect of herbicides on rice seedlings, offers opportunities to control

Effect of herbicides and cultural methods on grain yield, panicles m⁻², panicle weight, and weed dry weight in direct-seeded puddled rice. Pantnagar, India, 1993-94.

Treatment	Time of application (DAS) ^a	Dose (kg ai ha ⁻¹)	Concentration	1993				1994			
				Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles		Weed dry weight (g m ⁻²)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles		Weed dry weight (g m ⁻²)
					No. m ⁻²	Weight (g)			No. m ⁻²	Weight (g)	
Weed-free (check)		-	-	5.3	475	1.42	10	5.9	468	1.05	35
Hand weeding twice	20 and 40	-	-	5.1	357	1.66	91	5.4	486	1.18	175
High plant population (125 kg seed ha ⁻¹) + 1 hand weeding	20 (1993) 30 (1994)	-	-	2.5	432	0.98	247	-	-	-	-
				-	-	-	-	5.4	562	0.93	87
Pretilachlor + safener	3	0.4	30 EC ^b	3.7	392	1.23	305	3.7	512	0.99	563
Pretilachlor + safener	6	0.4	30 EC	2.6	378	0.93	430	-	-	-	-
Pretilachlor + safener	3	0.6	30 EC	4.7	400	1.06	225	4.4	463	1.06	304
Pretilachlor + safener	6	0.6	30 EC	4.6	385	1.39	267	-	-	-	-
Butachlor + safener	3	1.0	50 EC	3.4	322	1.22	279	3.4	484	0.87	678
Butachlor + safener	6	1.0	50 EC	3.0	358	1.08	394	-	-	-	-
Butachlor + safener	3	1.5	50 EC	3.6	373	1.07	422	4.1	498	0.89	357
Butachlor + safener	6	1.5	50 EC	4.0	355	1.16	404	-	-	-	-
Butachlor	3	1.0	50 EC	-	-	-	-	3.8	440	0.90	376
Butachlor	3	1.5	50 EC	3.4	389	1.30	305	3.4	425	0.85	444
Butachlor	6	1.5	50 EC	3.0	429	1.13	373	-	-	-	-
Anilophos	3	0.3	30 EC	-	-	-	-	1.5	244	0.69	601
Anilophos	3	0.4	30 EC	-	-	-	-	0.9	141	1.31	960
Anilophos	8	0.4	30 EC	3.7	391	1.15	360	3.5	355	1.05	356
Thiobencarb	3	1.0	50 EC	-	-	-	-	2.2	250	1.15	607
Thiobencarb	3	1.5	50 EC	-	-	-	-	1.9	202	1.06	678
Weedy (nonweeded control)		-	-	1.2	252	0.99	473	0.8	150	0.78	935
LSD (5%)				1.1	97	ns	200	1.5	150	0.34	213
CV (%)				21.0	18	26.00	46	23.0	28	24.00	31

^aDAS = days after seeding. ^bEC = emulsifiable concentrate.